

CORPORATE GOVERNANCE-BASED FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT: A NEUTROSOPHIC SWARA-RBNAR METHOD

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Abstract: Corporate governance reflects the managerial principles adopted by firms and influences various performance parameters. Companies with robust corporate governance mechanisms tend to establish a high level of trust with their stakeholders. This paper examines corporate governance parameters alongside financial indicators to provide insights into company performance. The primary objective of the study is to develop a robust decision support system for analyzing decision-making models based on corporate governance and financial performance indicators. In this context, a hybrid method combining single-valued triangular neutrosophic (SVTN), step-wise weight assessment ratio analysis (SWARA), and reference-based normalization alternative ranking (RBNAR) is proposed. The weights of the criteria affecting firm performance are determined using the SVTN-SWARA method, while firm performance levels based on these weights are obtained through the RBNAR approach. The SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method is applied to thirty-two companies listed in the Borsa Istanbul Corporate Governance Index over a three-year period (2021–2023). The core finding indicates that the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR method provides accurate and consistent company rankings,

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with AKSA achieving the highest performance. Among the financial criteria, net profit margin is identified as the most critical indicator. Within corporate governance parameters, the board of directors' score emerges as the most significant factor. The robustness of the proposed method is further reinforced through sensitivity analyses.

Keywords: *Financial Performance; Corporate Governance Index; Single-Valued Triangular Neutrosophic Sets; Step Wise Weight Assessment Ratio Analysis; Reference-Based Normalization Alternative Ranking*

1. Introduction

In a competitive global environment, the implementation of effective corporate governance practices provides companies with a competitive advantage (Filatotchev & Wright, 2011). The legal regulations and guidelines established to ensure a strong corporate governance structure support attracting investors' attention (Alregab, 2023). Moreover, these regulations help to build investor confidence (Bhatt & Bhatt, 2017). In addition, the set of rules developed for corporate governance enhances the auditability and transparency of companies (Salehi et al., 2023).

The crises experienced worldwide (such as COVID-19) Jebran and Chen (2023) and corporate scandals (including Enron, WorldCom, and Parmalat) Hilton and Arkorful (2021) have sparked significant discussions regarding corporate governance practices among firms. In this context, changes in corporate governance have also begun to take place in Turkey. The Corporate Governance Principles, adopted by the Capital Markets Board of Turkey (CMB) in 2003, were established based on the Corporate Governance Principles developed by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in 1999 (Ararat & Ugur, 2003; Jesover & Kirkpatrick, 2005). In 2005, publicly listed companies were required to incorporate statements on their adherence to these principles within their annual reports. According to the CMB, corporate governance ratings are a comprehensive collection of actions that are impartially, independently, and fairly assessed to ascertain how well businesses follow corporate governance principles (Sönmez, 2023). The OECD has established in Turkey the key principles of corporate governance, including shareholder rights (25%), public disclosure and transparency (25%), stakeholder engagement (15%), and the role of the board of directors (35%). As a result, the Corporate Governance Index was launched in 2007 (Saygili et al., 2022).

Corporate governance is one of the fundamental principles that delineates the management responsibilities of companies and strengthens the principles of transparency and accountability (Ellili, 2023; Salehi et al., 2023). This, in turn, contributes to establishing trust among investors and other stakeholders, as well-managed companies tend to be more successful in attaining sustainable growth targets. Additionally, corporate governance principles enable firms to enhance their risk management, utilize financial resources more efficiently, and fulfill their social responsibilities. In the literature, board composition, ownership structure (Khan & Mahmood, 2023; Khan et al., 2023), information disclosure transparency (Liu et al., 2023), and audit practices, are associated with company performance (Mardnly et al., 2018).

The aim of this paper is to develop a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM)-based

decision support system (DSS) that enables the use of corporate governance and financial indicators in assessing company performance. In this context, a hybrid method combining single-valued triangular neutrosophic (SVTN)–step wise weight assessment ratio analysis (SWARA)–reference-based normalization alternative ranking (RBNAR) is proposed. The SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR method represents a novel hybrid approach, as it integrates SVTN sets, the SWARA criterion weighting technique, and the RBNAR ranking method, while evaluating alternatives based on distances from reference points rather than relying solely on maximum–minimum values.

For the hybrid model, the decision-making framework was structured with the following: an expert group to determine the levels of criteria; financial ratio metrics and corporate governance parameters as criteria; and companies listed on BIST Corporate Governance Index as alternatives. The SVTN-SWARA method (Keršuliene et al., 2010) was applied to establish the significance levels of criteria, utilizing SVTN sets (Abdel-Basset & Mohamed, 2020) and linguistic variables to facilitate expert evaluations of criteria. The RBNAR method Kara et al. (2024) was used to calculate and rank companies' financial performance (FP) based on both corporate governance and financial ratios. The RBNAR method, a reference-based alternative ranking approach, was chosen for its ability to normalize criteria based on distances from reference values. Unlike conventional methods (TOPSIS, VIKOR, or EDAS), where criteria are typically defined as cost-based or benefit-based, RBNAR allows performance rankings to reflect the alignment of each criterion with established reference benchmarks, providing a more accurate assessment of FP.

1.1 Research Aims and Contributions

The primary aim of this research is to develop a decision support system (DSS) that integrates corporate governance performance with FP in order to evaluate corporate governance-based FP levels more comprehensively than traditional financial-only approaches. To achieve this, the study introduces and validates a novel hybrid methodology, SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR, which leverages SVTN sets for handling uncertainty, extends the SWARA method for nuanced criterion weighting through linguistic variables, and applies RBNAR with reference-based normalization to enhance ranking accuracy beyond conventional max-min techniques.

Empirical application of the proposed method to firms listed on the BIST Corporate Governance Index for the years 2021–2023 demonstrates the model's feasibility and robustness, while also enabling an analysis of performance shifts across years under external economic conditions such as high inflation in Turkey. The findings highlight net profit margin as the most critical financial criterion and the board of directors score as the most influential governance parameter, underscoring the method's capability to identify key drivers of corporate governance-based FP.

This study contributes to the literature by:

1. Presenting an innovative hybrid MCDM framework that uniquely combines SVTN sets, SWARA, and RBNAR.
2. Integrating corporate governance and FP indicators within a single evaluation model, thereby bridging a key gap in performance assessment research.
3. Introducing the first application of SVTN sets within SWARA to improve precision in weighting under uncertainty.

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4. Providing empirical validation with real-world corporate governance data from Borsa Istanbul.
5. Offering practical implications for investors, managers, and policymakers through a robust decision-support tool that reflects both governance structures and financial outcomes in corporate performance rankings.

The paper is structured into eight main sections. The Introduction presents the research aim and contributions, followed by the Literature Review, which examines performance analysis using MCDM approaches. The Methodology section details SVTN sets and the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method. In the Application section, the proposed method is applied to assess the corporate governance-based FP of BIST-listed firms from 2021 to 2023. The Results section evaluates the relative performance of these firms, while Sensitivity Analysis tests the robustness of the hybrid method. The Implications section discusses both research and managerial contributions, and the Conclusion summarizes key findings, study limitations, and directions for future research.

2. Literature Review

In the literature, financial and non-FP analyses of companies listed on various indexes are often conducted using different MCDM methods. Three distinct approaches are adopted in these studies. The first approach focuses solely on financial ratios to analyze companies' FP. The second approach, in contrast, emphasizes non-financial parameters in performance analysis. The third approach combines both financial and non-financial parameters for a comprehensive performance analysis. Compared to the first two, the third approach is less prevalent in literature. This research adopts the third approach, utilizing both financial and non-financial parameters for the FP analysis, where non-financial parameters are represented by corporate governance metrics. Consequently, the proposed method and approach in this study align with the third approach. The literature review in this research is structured based on these three approaches.

In the literature review focused on the first approach, studies that utilize financial ratios were examined. Recent studies have extensively applied financial ratios as key criteria for evaluating company performance across various markets and sectors using MCDM methods. Ghosh and Bhattacharya (2022) assessed companies in the hospitality and tourism sectors using MEREC and CoCoSo, while (Dağistanlı, 2023) applied the hesitant fuzzy set TOPSIS method to firms listed on the Istanbul Stock Exchange Sustainable Index. Lam et al. (2023) employed Fuzzy TOPSIS for Dow Jones Industrial Average companies, and (Sarigül et al., 2023) combined CRITIC, MAUT, and MARCOS to rank airline companies. Alsanousi et al. (2024) analyzed Saudi Stock Market firms using BWM and TOPSIS, whereas (Işık et al., 2024) integrated DEMATEL, CRITIC, EDAS, WASPAS, and TOPSIS for BIST-listed companies. Elma (2024) utilized FUCA, VIKOR, TOPSIS, SAW, CODAS, RAFSI, and GRA, for Istanbul Stock Exchange firms. (Kara et al., 2024) introduced hybrid methods such as single-valued neutrosophic-CIMAS-CRITIC-RBNAR and MEREC-RBNAR to assess technology and Sustainable Index companies. Çilek and Şeyranlıoğlu (2025) evaluated Turkish reinsurance companies using LODECI, CRADIS, and AROMAN, highlighting robust performance rankings, while (Katrancı et al., 2025) applied ITARA and COBRA for BIST 100 firms.

In the second phase of the literature review, studies that conducted performance analysis based on non-financial criteria were examined. Miguez et al. (2023) used AHP and TOPSIS for hotels, Hoang et al. (2024) employed spherical fuzzy AHP and WASPAS for ESG performance, Nguyen et al. (2024) used Pythagorean fuzzy AHP and CoCoSo, and Yüksel and Uncu (2024) applied EDAS for railway companies.

The third phase of the literature review examines studies that address performance analysis based on both financial and non-financial parameters. Ban et al. (2020) and Işık et al. (2025) assessed companies using both financial and non-financial indicators with MCDM methods, with this study using financial ratios for FP and service network and stock market metrics for non-FP.

Table 1 summarizes the literature, categorizing studies by financial, non-financial, and combined performance analyses, along with the methods used in each.

Table 1: Literature review.

Authors	Methods	Approaches
(Ban et al., 2020)	Fuzzy AHP and TOPSIS	Both FP and non-FP
(Ghosh & Bhattacharya, 2022)	MEREC and CoCoSo	FP
(Dağstanlı, 2023)	Hesitant fuzzy set TOPSIS	FP
(Lam et al., 2023)	Fuzzy TOPSIS	FP
(Miguez et al., 2023)	AHP-TOPSIS	Non-FP
(Sarigül et al., 2023)	CRITIC, MAUT, MARCOS	FP
(Alsanousi et al., 2024)	BWM and TOPSIS	FP
(Elma, 2024)	FUCA, VIKOR, TOPSIS, SAW, CODAS, RAFSI and GRA	FP
(Hoang et al., 2024)	Spherical fuzzy AHP and spherical fuzzy WASPAS	Non-FP
(Işık et al., 2024)	DEMATEL, CRITIC, EDAS, WASPAS and TOPSIS	FP
(Işık et al., 2025)	Pythagorean fuzzy AHP and MAIRCA	Both FP and non-FP
(Kara et al., 2024)	SVN-CIMAS-CRITIC-RBNAR	FP
(Nguyen et al., 2024)	Pythagorean fuzzy AHP and Pythagorean fuzzy CoCoSo	Non-FP
(Yüksel & Uncu, 2024)	EDAS	FP

Ultimately, upon reviewing the literature, it is assessed that most performance analyses conducted on companies are primarily based on financial ratios. This research adopts a corporate governance-focused perspective, considering both FP and corporate governance scores concurrently, thereby integrating both financial ratios and corporate governance scores into the analysis.

3. Methodology: The SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR Hybrid Method

In this paper, the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method is developed and proposed to calculate corporate governance-based FP. The application of this hybrid method is conducted in three phases. In Phase 1, the decision model inputs are defined, including the selection of experts, establishment of criteria (financial ratios and corporate governance parameters), identification of alternatives (BIST Corporate Governance Index companies), and construction of the reference values matrix for RBNAR. Phase 2 involves applying the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method in two stages: Stage 1 calculates criteria weights using SVTN-SWARA, and Stage 2 computes and ranks corporate governance-based FP using RBNAR. Finally, Phase 3 conducts sensitivity

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analysis to evaluate the robustness of the hybrid method. The framework of the methodology is shown in Fig. 1. Additionally, this section discusses SVTN set operations.

Figure 1: The SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR Hybrid Method.

A hybrid approach called "SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR" is developed to facilitate the determination of the performance of the companies. Let $(A_r) = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_{\mathfrak{R}}\}$ ($r = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{R}$) represents the companies as alternatives, $(F_q) = \{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_{\mathfrak{Q}}\}$ ($q = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{Q}$) represents the criteria, and $(G_p) = \{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_{\mathfrak{P}}\}$ ($p = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{P}$) represents the experts. The SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method steps are as follows:

Stage 1: Assess the criteria weighting matrix using the SVTN-SWARA method.

Step 1-1: Each criterion (F_q) can be evaluated by each expert (G_p) utilizing Table 2 which consists of linguistics variables (LVs). Then, LVs are converted to SVTN numbers. Thus, the initial decision matrix $(\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)} = [\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}]_{\mathfrak{Q}})$, where $\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)} = \left(\left(\tilde{T}_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}}(s), \tilde{I}_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}}(s), \tilde{F}_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}}(s) \right); \left(\vartheta_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}}, \mu_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}}, \pi_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}} \right) \right)$ ($q = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{Q}$; $p = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{P}$) for evaluating the criteria, is generated with SVTN numbers.

Table 2: Linguistics Variables for Evaluating Criteria (Grida et al., 2020).

Evaluation (level of alternatives)	SVTN sets
	$\left(\left(\tilde{T}_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}}(s), \tilde{I}_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}}(s), \tilde{F}_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}}(s) \right); \left(\vartheta_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}}, \mu_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}}, \pi_{\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}_q^{(p)}} \right) \right)$
Very Weakly Important (VWI)	$((0.10, 0.20, 0.30); (0.10, 0.20, 0.15))$
Weakly Important (WI)	$((0.15, 0.30, 0.50); (0.60, 0.20, 0.30))$
Partially Important (PI)	$((0.40, 0.35, 0.50); (0.60, 0.10, 0.20))$
Equal Important (EI)	$((0.50, 0.60, 0.70); (0.80, 0.10, 0.10))$
Strong Important (SI)	$((0.65, 0.70, 0.80); (0.90, 0.20, 0.10))$
Very Strong Important (VSI)	$((0.80, 0.75, 0.95); (0.70, 0.20, 0.20))$
Absolutely Important (AI)	$((0.95, 0.90, 0.95); (0.90, 0.10, 0.10))$

Step 1-2: By implementing Eq. (1), the average decision matrix ($\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q = [\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q]_{\mathcal{Q}}$), where $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q = \left(\left(\tilde{T}_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(s), \tilde{I}_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(s), \tilde{F}_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(s) \right); \left(\vartheta_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}, \mu_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}, \pi_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q} \right) \right)$ ($q = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{Q}$; $p = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{P}$), is computed with SVTN numbers:

$$\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q = \left(\left(\frac{\sum_{p=1}^{\mathfrak{P}} \tilde{T}_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(s)}{\mathfrak{P}}, \frac{\sum_{p=1}^{\mathfrak{P}} \tilde{I}_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(s)}{\mathfrak{P}}, \frac{\sum_{p=1}^{\mathfrak{P}} \tilde{F}_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(s)}{\mathfrak{P}} \right); \left(\frac{\sum_{p=1}^{\mathfrak{P}} \vartheta_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(p)}{\mathfrak{P}}, \frac{\sum_{p=1}^{\mathfrak{P}} \mu_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(p)}{\mathfrak{P}}, \frac{\sum_{p=1}^{\mathfrak{P}} \pi_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(p)}{\mathfrak{P}} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

Step 1-3: By implementing the score function ($\mathcal{S}(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q)$) presented in Eq. (2), the de-neutrosophic decision matrix ($\mathcal{D}_q = [\mathcal{D}_q]_{\mathcal{Q}}$) is determined:

$$\mathcal{D}_q = \mathcal{S}(\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q) = \frac{1}{8} \left(\left(\tilde{T}_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(s) + \tilde{I}_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(s) + \tilde{F}_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q}(s) \right) \left(2 + \vartheta_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q} - \mu_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q} - \pi_{\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_q} \right) \right); \quad (q = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{Q}). \quad (2)$$

Step 1-4: In this step, criteria are first ranked in descending order of importance based on their score function values (\mathcal{D}_q). Then, each criterion is subtracted from the previous one (Eq. (3)), calculating the score values to form the score values matrix ($\mathfrak{R}_q = [\mathfrak{R}_q]_{\mathcal{Q}}$):

$$\mathfrak{R}_q = (\mathcal{D}_{q-1} - \mathcal{D}_q); \quad (q = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{Q}). \quad (3)$$

Step 1-5: By implementing Eq. (4), the comparative coefficient matrix ($\mathfrak{M}_q = [\mathfrak{M}_q]_{\mathcal{Q}}$) is calculated:

$$\mathfrak{M}_q = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{for } q = 1 \\ (\mathfrak{R}_q + 1); & \text{for } q > 1 \end{cases}; \quad (q = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{Q}). \quad (4)$$

Step 1-6: By implementing Eq. (5), the weighting comparative coefficient matrix ($\mathcal{Q}_q = [\mathcal{Q}_q]_{\mathcal{Q}}$) is calculated:

$$\mathcal{Q}_q = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{for } q = 1 \\ \left(\frac{\mathfrak{M}_{q-1}}{\mathfrak{M}_q} \right); & \text{for } q > 1 \end{cases}; \quad (q = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{Q}). \quad (5)$$

Step 1-7: By implementing Eq. (6), the criteria weighting matrix ($\omega_q = [\omega_q]_{\mathcal{Q}}$) is calculated:

$$\omega_q = \frac{\mathcal{Q}_q}{\sum_{q=1}^{\mathcal{Q}} \mathcal{Q}_q}; \quad (q = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{Q}), \quad (6)$$

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herein, $\varpi_q = (\varpi_1, \varpi_2, \dots, \varpi_q, \dots, \varpi_\Omega)$ for $\varpi_q \in [0,1]$ with the $\sum_{q=1}^{\Omega} \varpi_q = 1$.

Stage 2: Computing the alternatives ranking matrix using the RBNAR method.

Step 2-1: The initial decision matrix ($\mathfrak{K}_{rq} = [\mathfrak{K}_{rq}]_{\mathfrak{R} \times \Omega}$) for evaluating the companies (alternatives) depending on the criteria is constructed.

Step 2-2a: The first normalization decision matrix ($\mathfrak{S}_{rq} = [\mathfrak{S}_{rq}]_{\mathfrak{R} \times \Omega}$) is calculated by implementing the “Z-score normalization technique” (Shih et al., 2007) presented in Eq. (7):

$$\mathfrak{S}_{rq} = e^{\left(\frac{\mathfrak{K}_{rq} - \mathbb{R}_q}{-2(\sigma_q)^2}\right)}; (r = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{R}; q = 1, 2, \dots, \Omega), \quad (7)$$

herein, σ_q is represent the standard deviation and \mathbb{R}_q represent the reference value for each criterion.

Step 2-2b: The second normalization decision matrix ($\mathfrak{T}_{rq} = [\mathfrak{T}_{rq}]_{\mathfrak{R} \times \Omega}$) is calculated using “Aytekin's reference-based normalization technique” (Aytekin, 2021) presented in Eq. (8):

$$\mathfrak{T}_{rq} = 1 - \frac{|\mathfrak{K}_{rq} - \mathbb{R}_q|}{|\mathbb{R}_q| + 10^\delta}; (r = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{R}; q = 1, 2, \dots, \Omega), \quad (8)$$

herein, δ is used for the positive parameter and \mathbb{R}_q is the reference value for each criterion.

Step 2-2c: The aggregated normalization decision matrix ($\mathfrak{D}_{rq} = [\mathfrak{D}_{rq}]_{\mathfrak{R} \times \Omega}$) is calculated using Heron Mean (Zhu, 2022) presented in Eq. (9):

$$\mathfrak{D}_{rq} = \left(\beta \sqrt{\mathfrak{S}_{rq} \mathfrak{T}_{rq}} + (1 - \beta) \frac{\mathfrak{S}_{rq} + \mathfrak{T}_{rq}}{2}\right); (r = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{R}; q = 1, 2, \dots, \Omega), \quad (9)$$

wherein, $\beta \in [0,1]$ is the trade of parameter for assessing the significance level of aggregated normalization.

Step 2-3: The weighted aggregated normalization decision matrix ($\mathfrak{B}_{rq} = [\mathfrak{B}_{rq}]_{\mathfrak{R} \times \Omega}$) is calculated using Eq. (10):

$$\mathfrak{B}_{rq} = (\varpi_q \mathfrak{D}_{rq}); (r = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{R}; q = 1, 2, \dots, \Omega), \quad (10)$$

herein, $\varpi_q = (\varpi_1, \varpi_2, \dots, \varpi_q, \dots, \varpi_\Omega)$ for $\varpi_q \in [0,1]$ with the $\sum_{q=1}^{\Omega} \varpi_q = 1$.

Step 2-4: The alternative ranking matrix ($\mathfrak{A}_r = [\mathfrak{A}_r]_{\mathfrak{R}}$) is calculated using Eq. (11).

$$\mathfrak{A}_r = \sum_{q=1}^{\Omega} \mathfrak{B}_{rq}; (r = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{R}). \quad (11)$$

The alternative with the highest \mathfrak{A}_r value is defined as having the best performance. The diagram of the hybrid method is presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Diagram of the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method.

4. Applications

This paper evaluate the corporate governance-based FP of companies listed on the BIST Corporate Governance Index using the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method. The index includes BIST-listed companies that have obtained a minimum score of seven in each sub-component and an overall corporate governance rating above eight. A total of 74 companies is included in this index, of which 20 are banking and financial institutions. Due to differences in reporting standards within the financial sector, comparable analysis between these institutions and non-financial companies is not feasible. As a result, banking and financial institutions were excluded from the scope

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of the applications. Additionally, 22 holding companies prepare consolidated financial reports that encompass information from their subsidiaries. These consolidated reports preclude comparable analysis, and therefore, holding companies were also excluded from the scope of the analysis. Ultimately, this study focused on assessing the financial and non-FP of 32 companies that were neither classified under the banking and finance sectors nor as holding companies.

Annual data from 2021 to 2023 were used to assess FP and corporate governance performance of the selected companies. Financial ratios were calculated, and corporate governance scores were obtained from the Public Disclosure Platform. This section defines the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR inputs and presents performance analyses for 2021–2023.

4.1 Experts, Criteria, and BIST Corporate Governance Index Companies

4.1.1 Identification of Experts

To calculate FP of companies included in the BIST Corporate Governance Index based on corporate governance principles, a hybrid model combining SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR methods is employed. This hybrid model requires expert opinions to determine the significant levels of FP criteria and corporate governance parameters, which are defined as the evaluation parameters.

The expert group comprised 10 professionals with expertise in financial ratios and corporate governance. The panel included academics and researchers in finance and accounting, corporate executives such as CEOs and CFOs, a financial reporting manager, a corporate investment bank CEO, a corporate governance and sustainability director, and an experienced financial advisor. The professional titles of these experts are presented in Table 3. Experts were informed that their evaluations might be subjective and were guided to determining the relative financial importance of the individual criteria.

Table 3: The expert group.

Experts	Professions
G_1 – 1 st expert	Head of the center for corporate governance and sustainability.
G_2 – 2 nd expert	Chief financial officer with 30 years of experience.
G_3 – 3 rd expert	Academic researcher in corporate governance and financial management.
G_4 – 4 th expert	Financial reporting manager with 15 years of experience.
G_5 – 5 th expert	General manager of an investment bank.
G_6 – 6 th expert	Professor conducting research in accounting and finance
G_7 – 7 th expert	Associate Professor conducting research in finance
G_8 – 8 th expert	Financial advisor with 25 years of experience
G_9 – 9 th expert	Associate Professor conducting research in finance
G_{10} – 10 th expert	Chief financial officer with 18 years of experience.

4.1.2 Identification of Financial Performance Criteria

In this decision model, 10 financial ratios were used to evaluate the performance of companies, while five corporate governance rating scores were utilized to assess their corporate governance performance. The selected financial ratios provide insights into the companies' liquidity, profitability, efficiency, leverage, turnover, and market performance; therefore, they were chosen as the financial criteria. On the other hand, the corporate governance rating scores offer information on their corporate governance performance. The financial ratios and corporate governance rating scores

considered as criteria in the decision model are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Computation of criteria and source reports.

Criteria	Formula	Source/Reference
“Current ratio (F_1)”	$F_1 = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$	(Abdel-Basset et al., 2020)
“Return on equity (F_2)”	$F_2 = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Shareholders' Equity}} * 100$	(Kara et al., 2024)
“Return on assets ratio (F_3)”	$F_3 = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Assets}} * 100$	(Akdemir & Şimşek, 2023)
“Receivables turnover (F_4)”	$F_4 = \frac{\text{Net Credit Sales}}{\text{Average Accounts Receivable}}$	(Dao & Phan, 2023)
“Leverage ratio (F_5)”	$F_5 = \frac{\text{Total Liabilities}}{\text{Total Assets}}$	(Kalaycıoğlu & Kurtaran, 2024)
“Debt to equity ratio (F_6)”	$F_6 = \frac{\text{Total Liabilities}}{\text{Shareholders' Equity}}$	(Abdel-Basset & Mohamed, 2020)
“Tobin’s Q (F_7)”	$F_7 = \frac{\text{Market Value of Firm}}{\text{Replacement Cost of Assets}}$	(Aydoğmuş et al., 2022)
“Operating profit margin (F_8)”	$F_8 = \frac{\text{Operating Income}}{\text{Net Sales}} * 100$	(Mao, 2024)
“Pre-tax profit margin (F_9)”	$F_9 = \frac{\text{Pre - Tax Profit}}{\text{Net Sales}} * 100$	(Lu & Wang, 2024)
“Net profit margin (F_{10})”	$F_{10} = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Net Sales}} * 100$	(Abdel-Basset et al., 2020)
“Shareholders score (F_{11})”	Scores assigned to companies in the corporate governance index	(Index, 2024)
“Public disclosure and transparency score (F_{12})”		
“Stakeholders score (F_{13})”		
“Board of directors score (F_{14})”		
“Corporate governance index score (F_{15})”		

The criteria included in the decision model are as follows:

Current ratio (F_1) – The current ratio, defined as the proportion of current assets to current liabilities, serves as a key indicator of a company’s short-term debt-paying capacity and liquidity, though it alone is insufficient to guarantee long-term operational sustainability and must be considered alongside other financial metrics when assessing overall corporate performance (Abdel-Basset & Mohamed, 2020).

Return on equity (F_2) – Return on equity (ROE) is employed as a key measure of shareholder profitability relative to invested equity, offering insights into a firm’s financial position over time while also reflecting the effects of shareholder investment decisions, including those related to environmental initiatives, on overall FP (Bunea et al., 2019). ROE is a key indicator of how efficiently a firm manages shareholders’ equity, with higher values signaling competitive advantage through greater profitability and investor returns.

Return on assets ratio (F_3) – This ratio, reflecting net income relative to total assets, serves as a key financial metric for assessing asset utilization and is employed as a parameter in the FP evaluation (Akdemir & Şimşek, 2023).

Receivables turnover (F_4) – The receivables turnover ratio measures the efficiency of fund collection within a given period, with higher values indicating effective credit

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sales management and the potential to enhance profitability (Sunaryo & Lestari, 2023).

Leverage ratio (F_5) – The leverage ratio indicates the extent to which a company's financing is sourced from debt. It is computed by dividing the total of short-term and long-term liabilities by the company's total assets (Kalaycıoğlu & Kurtaran, 2024).

Debt to equity ratio (F_6) – This ratio, as one of the primary capital structure ratios, has a immense impact on a firm's long-term profitability. The financial leverage position of a company can leads capital structure ratios exhibiting both positive and negative correlations with the firm's FP (Abdel-Basset & Mohamed, 2020).

Tobin's Q (F_7) – This criterion reflects the relationship between a company's market value and its replacement cost, calculated as the market value divided by the cost of replacing its assets. It is commonly used to assess whether a firm is over- or undervalued. Due to the challenges in precisely estimating total asset replacement costs, analysts often apply specific formulas to calculate Tobin's Q (Aydoğmuş et al., 2022).

Operating profit margin (F_8) – Operating profit margin represents the proportion of operating profit relative to net sales, expressed as a percentage. It is calculated by dividing the annual operating profit by operating income, providing insight into the profitability from core business operations (Mao, 2024).

Pre-tax profit margin (F_9) – The pretax profit rate is calculated as the firm's total annual profit divided by its total revenue, expressed as a percentage (Lu & Wang, 2024). This ratio indicates pre-tax profitability from core operations, with higher margins reflecting stronger performance and lower margins signaling potential concerns.

Net profit margin (F_{10}) – This criterion measures the proportion of revenue converted into net profit, reflecting management's effectiveness in controlling costs and enhancing investor confidence (Abdel-Basset & Mohamed, 2020).

Shareholders score (F_{11}) – This criterion provides an assessment of the shareholders that companies possess. When the parameter value is high, it indicates that the companies have higher-quality shareholders. Additionally, a strong shareholder's score reflects good corporate governance (Index, 2024).

Public disclosure and transparency score (F_{12}) – This criterion reflects a company's transparency in financial reporting, serving as an indicator of effective corporate governance, enhancing stakeholder trust, and supporting informed decision-making regarding FP (Index, 2024).

Stakeholders score (F_{13}) – This criterion, which impacts the corporate governance score, indicates the level of responsibility and accountability that companies have towards their shareholders. Companies with a high parameter value also tend to have greater corporate governance success. Particularly, the management of the company in conjunction with its stakeholders and the overall success can be understood through this parameter (Index, 2024).

Board of directors score (F_{14}) – This criterion reflects the quality and effectiveness of managers. In strategic decision-making, it is essential to have managers who adopt corporate governance principles and operate in accordance with them. Therefore, companies with a highly effective board of directors are expected to also exhibit high

corporate governance success (Index, 2024).

Corporate governance index scores (F_{15}) – This criterion reflects the overall score of the index. The primary reason for including the overall score in the decision model is to observe the simultaneous effects of both the sub-parameters and the overall score in the performance analysis (Index, 2024).

4.1.3 Identification of Companies

This case study evaluates FP of companies listed on the BIST Corporate Governance Index. Of the 74 companies in the index, 25 banking and finance firms were excluded due to non-comparability, and 17 additional companies were removed due to missing corporate governance reports required for five selected evaluation criteria. Consequently, 32 companies were analyzed using financial statements from 2021 to 2023. Financial ratios were calculated for each firm, and an initial decision matrix was constructed to support further analysis. The companies included in the study are detailed in Table 5.

Table 5: Corporate Governance Index companies listed on BIST.

Codes	Companies	Year of index participation
A ₁ AKSA	“AKSA Akriklik Kimya Sanayii Inc.”	2014
A ₂ AKSEN	“AKSA Energy Production Inc.”	2021
A ₃ AEFES	“Anadolu Efes Beverage Industry Inc.”	2008
A ₄ ARCLK	“Arçelik Inc.”	2009
A ₅ ASELS	“ASELSAN Electronic Industries and Trade Inc.”	2012
A ₆ AYGAZ	“Aygaz Inc.”	2010
A ₇ BTCIM	“Batiçim West Anatolian Cement Industry Inc.”	2019
A ₈ CCOLA	“Coca-Cola İçecek Inc.”	2009
A ₉ DOAS	“Doğuş Automotive Service ad Trade Inc.”	2011
A ₁₀ ENJSA	“Enerjisa Energy Inc.”	2019
A ₁₁ ENKAI	“Enka Construction and Industry Inc.”	2012
A ₁₂ EREGL	“Ereğli Iron and Steel Factories Inc.”	2015
A ₁₃ HURGZ	“Hürriyet Journalism and Printing Inc.”	2007
A ₁₄ IHEVA	“İhlas Home Appliances Manufacturing Industry and Trade Inc.”	2011
A ₁₅ ISDMR	“İskenderun Iron and Steel Inc.”	2020
A ₁₆ LOGO	“Logo Software Industry and Trade Inc.”	2009
A ₁₇ MGROS	“Migros Trade Inc.”	2015
A ₁₈ OTKAR	“Otokar Automotive and Defense Industry Inc.”	2008
A ₁₉ PRKME	“Park Electricity Production Mining Industry and Trade Inc.”	2011
A ₂₀ PGSUS	“Pegasus Airlines Inc.”	2013
A ₂₁ PETUN	“Pınar Integrated Meat and Flour Industry Inc.”	2012
A ₂₂ PINSU	“Pınar Water and Beverage Industry and Trade Inc.”	2013
A ₂₃ PNSUT	“Pınar Dairy Products Industry Inc.”	2011
A ₂₄ QUAGR	“QUA Granite Hayal Constr. and Products Industry Trade Inc.”	2021
A ₂₅ TATGD	“Tat Gıda Sanayi Inc.”	2021
A ₂₆ TOASO	“TOFAŞ Turkish Automobile Factory Inc.”	2007
A ₂₇ TUPRS	“Tüpraş-Türkiye Petrol Rafinerileri A.Ş.”	2007
A ₂₈ PRKAB	“Turk Prysmian Cable and Systems Inc.”	2010
A ₂₉ TTKOM	“Turk Telecommunication Inc.”	2010
A ₃₀ TTRAK	“Turk Tractor and Agricultural Machinery Inc.”	2007
A ₃₁ SISE	“Turkey Glass and Bottle Factories Inc.”	2014
A ₃₂ VESTL	“Vestel Electronics Industry and Trade Inc.”	2007

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4.2 Application-1: Evaluation of Financial Performance for 2023

FP of the companies included in the BIST Corporate Governance Index for the year 2023 were ranked using the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method by applying the algorithmic steps:

Application-1 – Stage 1: Computing the criteria weighting matrix using the SVTN-SWARA method.

Using Table 2, each expert evaluated the criteria with LVs, which were subsequently converted into SVTN numbers. The criterion assessment matrices are presented in Table S.1 (LVs) and Table S.2 (SVTN numbers). The average decision matrix based on SVTN numbers was computed using Eq. (1) and is shown in Table S.3. The de-neutrosophic decision matrix was then derived using the score function in Eq. (2) and presented in Table S.4. Following this, the score values matrix was calculated via Eq. (3), and the comparative coefficient matrix and weighting comparative coefficient matrix were determined using Eq. (4) and Eq. (5), respectively, as shown in Table S.5. Finally, the criteria weighing matrix ($\varpi_q = [\varpi_q]_{\Omega}$) was obtained using Eq. (6) and is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: The criteria-weighting matrix ($\varpi_q = [\varpi_q]_{\Omega}$).

	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆	F ₇	F ₈	F ₉	F ₁₀	F ₁₁	F ₁₂	F ₁₃	F ₁₄	F ₁₅
ϖ_q	0.058	0.074	0.067	0.063	0.064	0.060	0.063	0.071	0.074	0.079	0.064	0.063	0.065	0.065	0.065
ϖ_q	7	1	4	4	1	4	5	2	2	8	0	4	0	5	3

Application-1 – Stage 2: Computing the alternatives ranking matrix using the RBNAR method.

The initial decision matrix for evaluating companies in 2023 based on the selected criteria was constructed and is presented in Table S.6. The first normalized decision matrix was calculated using Eq. (7) and is shown in Table S.7, while the reference matrix is provided in Table S.8. Subsequently, the second normalization matrix was obtained via Eq. (8) ($\delta = 4$) and presented in Table S.9, followed by the aggregated normalization decision matrix calculated using Eq. (9) and shown in Table S.10. The weighted aggregated normalization matrix was then computed using Eq. (10) ($\beta = 0.5$), incorporating the criteria weighting matrix from Table 6, and is presented in Table S.11. Finally, the alternative ranking matrix ($\mathfrak{A}_r = [\mathfrak{A}_r]_{\mathfrak{R}}$) was determined using Eq. (11) and is provided in Table 7.

Table 7: BIST Corporate Governance Index companies' rankings.

Companies	Application-1 (2023)		Application-2 (2022)		Application-3 (2021)	
	\mathfrak{A}_r	Rank	\mathfrak{A}_r	Rank	\mathfrak{A}_r	Rank
A ₁ AKSA	0.931158	1	0.920168	1	0.943101	1
A ₂₇ TUPRS	0.915119	2	0.877908	5	0.888831	7
A ₃₁ SISE	0.914471	3	0.886018	3	0.902997	5
A ₃ AEFES	0.90716	4	0.907091	2	0.917611	3
A ₁₀ ENJSA	0.901276	5	0.855569	9	0.899449	6
A ₁₂ EREGL	0.895858	6	0.855649	8	0.835324	18
A ₁₅ ISDMR	0.89475	7	0.814483	19	0.79321	24
A ₆ AYGAZ	0.884071	8	0.83001	14	0.86859	10
A ₄ ARCLK	0.86469	9	0.883087	4	0.925955	2
A ₂₉ TTKOM	0.854024	10	0.825228	16	0.86006	13
A ₂₂ PINSU	0.851711	11	0.776104	24	0.795802	23

Table 7: BIST Corporate Governance Index companies' rankings. (cont...)

A ₁₇	MGROS	0.849312	12	0.774464	25	0.760641	27
A ₂₅	TATGD	0.848434	13	0.863076	7	0.877404	9
A ₃₂	VESTL	0.846337	14	0.849147	10	0.912346	4
A ₂₀	PGSUS	0.835062	15	0.846176	11	0.808101	21
A ₉	DOAS	0.826762	16	0.822195	17	0.853646	15
A ₁₆	LOGO	0.821543	17	0.795517	23	0.826262	20
A ₂₁	PETUN	0.818947	18	0.802074	22	0.840784	16
A ₂₃	PNSUT	0.817873	19	0.804479	21	0.839507	17
A ₁₈	OTKAR	0.80522	20	0.812485	20	0.858572	14
A ₅	ASELS	0.802119	21	0.833356	13	0.831092	19
A ₂	AKSEN	0.79717	22	0.845864	12	0.862886	12
A ₈	CCOLA	0.784534	23	0.872278	6	0.878621	8
A ₂₈	PRKAB	0.777435	24	0.825498	15	0.867226	11
A ₃₀	TTRAK	0.777251	25	0.82085	18	0.745938	28
A ₁₁	ENKAI	0.773257	26	0.750767	26	0.801534	22
A ₂₄	QUAGR	0.771346	27	0.726862	28	0.669225	30
A ₂₆	TOASO	0.761363	28	0.749784	27	0.776662	26
A ₇	BTCIM	0.744421	29	0.614073	31	0.65329	31
A ₁₉	PRKME	0.615394	30	0.601206	32	0.630945	32
A ₁₄	IHEVA	0.59931	31	0.652791	30	0.67174	29
A ₁₃	HURGZ	0.555098	32	0.714	29	0.781648	25

4.3 Application-2: Evaluation of Financial Performance for 2022

The performance of the companies for the year 2022 were ranked using the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method by applying algorithmic steps. In Application-2, the criteria weighting matrix ($\varpi_q = [\varpi_q]_{\Omega}$) presented in Application-1 – Steps 1-7 was used.

Application-2 – Stage 2: Computing the alternatives ranking matrix using the RBNAR method.

The initial decision matrix for evaluating companies in 2022 based on the selected criteria was constructed and is presented in Table S.12. The first normalized decision matrix was computed using Eq. (7) and shown in Table S.13, while the reference values for each criterion and the corresponding reference value matrix are provided in Table S.14. The second normalized decision matrix was then calculated using Eq. (8) ($\delta = 4$) and presented in Table S.15, followed by the aggregated normalization decision matrix obtained via Eq. (9) and shown in Table S.16. The weighted aggregated normalization decision matrix was derived using Eq. (10) ($\beta = 0.5$), incorporating the criteria weighting matrix from Table 6, and is presented in Table S.17. Finally, the alternative ranking matrix ($\mathcal{R}_r = [\mathcal{R}_r]_{\mathcal{R}}$) was determined using Eq. (11) and is reported in Table 7.

4.4 Application-3: Evaluation of Financial Performance for 2021

The performance of the companies for the year 2021 were ranked using the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method by applying algorithmic steps. In Application-3, the criteria weighting matrix ($\varpi_q = [\varpi_q]_{\Omega}$) presented in Application-1 – Steps 1-7 was used.

Application-3 – Stage 2: Computing the alternatives ranking matrix using the

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RBNAR method.

For the year 2023, the initial decision matrix based on the defined criteria was constructed and presented in Table S.18. The first stage of normalization was performed using Eq. (7), with the results reported in Table S.19, while the reference value matrix is provided in Table S.20. Subsequently, the second normalized decision matrix was obtained through Eq. (8) and presented in Table S.21. The aggregated normalization decision matrix was then derived using Eq. (9) and is shown in Table S.22. Incorporating the criteria weights from Table 6, the weighted aggregated normalization decision matrix was calculated using Eq. (10) and presented in Table S.23. Finally, the alternative ranking matrix was produced with Eq. (11) and is summarized in Table 7.

5. Results and Discussion

In this paper, the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR is developed and proposed for analyzing performance based on corporate governance. Companies listed on the Borsa Istanbul Index and participating in the Corporate Governance Index have been examined through three different case studies. Application-1 focuses on the year 2023, Application-2 on 2022, and Application-3 on 2021. The decision model includes criteria and companies, and the significance levels of the criteria in the decision-making process are calculated using the SVTN-SWARA method. Expert opinions were utilized at this stage. In calculating FP based on corporate governance, both financial ratios and corporate governance index parameters are defined as criteria, allowing all criteria to be evaluated by experts.

The ranking of criteria based on their weights was obtained as follows: "net profit margin" (F_{10}) > "pre-tax profit margin" (F_9) > "return on equity" (F_2) > "operating profit margin" (F_8) > "return on assets ratio" (F_3) > "board of directors score" (F_{14}) > "corporate governance index score" (F_{15}) > "stakeholders score" (F_{13}) > "leverage ratio" (F_5) > "shareholders score" (F_{11}) > "Tobin's Q" (F_7) > "receivables turnover" (F_4) > "public disclosure and transparency score" (F_{12}) > "debt to equity ratio" (F_6) > "current ratio" (F_1). According to this ranking, the criterion with the strongest influence in the decision-making process is identified as the "net profit margin" (F_{10}). Thus, "net profit margin" emerges as the most important parameter in calculating FP based on corporate governance. Additionally, among the corporate governance parameters, the "board of directors score" (F_{14}) criterion is identified as more effective than other corporate governance parameters. Moreover, in calculating FP based on corporate governance, the "current ratio" (F_1) criterion is determined to be the least important, falling behind all other parameters.

Since 2021, Turkey has experienced high inflation that peaked in 2022 but gradually decreased its impact in 2023. Therefore, this study aims to observe FP of companies based on corporate governance while developing case studies. The SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method was applied for the years 2021, 2022, and 2023, and performance levels were identified. Differences in performance values are shown in Fig. 3, while differences in performance rankings are presented in Fig. 4.

Figure 3: The performance values of the applications.

Examining the radar chart presented in Fig. 3 yields several observations regarding company performance over the period 2021–2023. AKSA consistently demonstrates the highest performance across all years, establishing itself as the top-performing company.

Comparing 2022 to 2021, seven companies—namely ASELS, MGROS, EREGL, ISDMR, PGSUS, QUAGR, and TTRAK—exhibited improvements in their performance. In contrast, 25 companies, including HURGZ, VESTL, ENKAI, OTKAR, ENJSA, ARCLK, PRKAB, BTCIM, PETUN, AYGAZ, PNSUT, TTKOM, DOAS, LOGO, PRKME, TOASO, AKSA, PINSU, IHEVA, AKSEN, SISE, TATGD, TUPRS, AEFES, and CCOLA, experienced a decline in their performance values.

In 2023, relative to 2022, 20 companies showed performance improvements, including AEFES, DOAS, AKSA, TOASO, PNSUT, PRKME, PETUN, ENKAI, LOGO, SISE, TTKOM, TUPRS, EREGL, QUAGR, ENJSA, AYGAZ, MGROS, PINSU, ISDMR, and BTCIM, while 12 companies, namely HURGZ, CCOLA, IHEVA, AKSEN, PRKAB, TTRAK, ASELS, ARCLK, TATGD, PGSUS, OTKAR, and VESTL, experienced performance declines.

Comparing the overall period from 2021 to 2023, 12 companies—ENJSA, SISE, AYGAZ, TUPRS, PGSUS, TTRAK, PINSU, EREGL, MGROS, BTCIM, ISDMR, and QUAGR—improved their performance, whereas 20 companies, including HURGZ, CCOLA, PRKAB, IHEVA, VESTL, AKSEN, ARCLK, OTKAR, ASELS, TATGD, ENKAI, DOAS, PETUN, PNSUT, PRKME, TOASO, AKSA, AEFES, TTKOM, and LOGO, exhibited decreased performance values. These results suggest that inflation, which began in 2021, negatively impacted performance indicators in 2022, followed by a recovery in 2023.

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Notably, BTCIM recorded the largest improvement in performance, emerging as the top performer in 2023 compared to 2022. Conversely, HURGZ experienced the greatest decline, registering the lowest performance in 2023 compared to 2021.

Analyzing the results presented in Fig. 4 yields several observations regarding changes in performance rankings over the period 2021–2023. Compared to 2022, 2023 saw improvements in the performance rankings of 15 companies, including MGROS, PINSU, ISDMR, TTKOM, LOGO, AYGAZ, ENJSA, PETUN, TUPRS, EREGL, BTCIM, PRKME, PNSUT, QUAGR, and DOAS, while rankings declined for 13 companies. The rankings of four companies—SISE, AKSA, ENKAI, and OTKAR—remained unchanged.

Figure 4: The performance rankings of the applications.

From 2021 to 2022, 12 companies, namely EREGL, PGSUS, TTRAK, ASELS, ISDMR, MGROS, TUPRS, QUAGR, SISE, TATGD, COLLA, and AEFES, showed improvements in their performance rankings, whereas 16 companies experienced declines. Four companies—BTCIM, PRKME, AKSA, and AKSEN—maintained the same rankings over this period.

Comparing 2021 to 2023, 15 companies—ISDMR, MGROS, PINSU, EREGL, PGSUS, TUPRS, TTKOM, LOGO, QUAGR, TTRAK, AYGAZ, BTCIM, PRKME, SISE, and ENJSA—improved their rankings, while 16 companies experienced a decline. Only AKSA maintained a consistent ranking throughout the period. These observations indicate significant fluctuations in corporate performance rankings over the examined years. Overall, it can be concluded that inflation has substantially influenced the FP rankings of companies in relation to corporate governance:

Ultimately, the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method is supported as an appropriate approach for calculating FP of companies based on corporate governance through the successful application in three different case studies.

6. Sensitivity Analyses

Sensitivity analyses are conducted based on sensitivity analysis scenarios (SAS) to test the reliability of SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR developed for calculating FP based on corporate governance. In the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method, two SAS scenarios are developed for Application-1, considering different values assigned to trade-off parameters. In SAS-1.1, different values are assigned to the δ parameter used in the second normalization step of the RBNAR method to obtain the performance rankings of companies. In SAS-1.2, values between 0 and 1 are assigned to the β parameter, which represents the trade-off value of two normalized values aggregated by the Heron Mean in the RBNAR method, to derive company performance rankings.

In SAS-1.1, values of 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 are assigned to the δ parameter, and the companies' performance rankings are determined. Fig. 5 presents the performance rankings of the companies, revealing that the rankings align with the original research findings. According to SAS-1.1, this indicates that the results of SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR are robust.

Figure 5: Performance rankings of SAS-1.1.

In SAS-1.2, values between 0 and 1 are assigned to the β parameter, and the algorithm is re-run. Fig. 6 shows the companies' performance rankings. While slight deviations in performance rankings are observed with changes in the β parameter, there are no major differences in the overall rankings. The correlation of the rankings in SAS-1.2 exceeds 0.98. Therefore, according to SAS-1.2, the results of SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR are confirmed as reliable.

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Figure 6: Performance rankings of SAS-1.2.

For Application-2, two additional SAS scenarios were developed, with numbers assigned to the δ and β parameters as in Application-1, and performance rankings were obtained. In SAS-2.1, the numbers 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 were again assigned to the δ parameter, resulting in the same performance rankings as those obtained in Application-2, as shown in Fig. 7. Thus, the robustness of the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method is further supported within Application-2.

Figure 7: Performance rankings of SAS-2.1.

In SAS-2.2, values between 0 and 1 were reassigned to the β parameter, with the resulting company performance rankings displayed in Fig. 8. The correlation of the rankings in SAS-2.2 exceeds 0.98. Although minor variations in rankings are observed in this scenario, the company with the best performance is still identified as AKSA. This

again confirms the reliability of the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method.

Figure 8: Performance rankings of SAS-2.2.

For Application-3, sensitivity analyses were conducted as in Application-1 and Application-2. Performance rankings based on values assigned to the δ parameter are shown in Fig. 9 (SAS-3.1), while rankings based on values assigned to the β parameter are displayed in Fig. 10 (SAS-3.2).

Figure 9: Performance rankings of AS-3.1.

The correlation of the rankings in SAS-3.2 exceeds 0.99. The rankings obtained in SAS-3.1 are identical to the rankings in Application-3. Although minor differences appear in the results of SAS-3.2, the overall ranking remains consistent. These findings

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further confirm the robustness of the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method.

Figure 10: Performance rankings of SAS-3.2.

7. Research and Managerial Implications

This study presents several significant implications for both research and managerial practices, enhancing the understanding and application of integrated performance assessment models in corporate governance and FP.

Notable research implications are:

Advancement of MCDM methodology – The introduction of the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method contributes to the existing MCDM literature by integrating linguistic variables and SVTN sets, providing a novel approach for performance evaluation. Future studies could explore the application of this hybrid method across different sectors or countries, thereby enriching the comparative analysis within corporate governance research.

Cross-disciplinary insights – The findings underscore the interrelationship between corporate governance and FP, suggesting that research could expand into other disciplines such as organizational behavior, ethics, and strategic management. Future researchers are encouraged to examine how these domains influence or are influenced by corporate governance practices, thus fostering a more holistic view of organizational success.

Empirical validation of governance indicators – The study’s identification of key indicators avenues for further empirical research to validate and refine these governance metrics. Researchers could investigate how these indicators correlate with long-term organizational performance and sustainability, thus contributing to the development of a more robust framework for governance assessments.

Significant managerial implications are:

Informed decision-making – By utilizing SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR, managers can gain

a comprehensive understanding of their organization's performance, incorporating both financial ratios and governance parameters. This dual perspective enables better-informed strategic decisions that align with both profitability and governance quality.

Focus on governance improvements – The identification of critical governance parameters, such as the "board of directors score", highlights the need for organizations to prioritize governance practices actively. Managers should consider investing in governance training and initiatives to enhance the effectiveness of their boards, ultimately leading to improved FP.

Performance benchmarking – The study provides a benchmarking tool for organizations listed on the Borsa İstanbul, enabling them to assess their performance relative to peers in terms of both financial ratios and governance standards. This benchmarking can drive competitive improvement and facilitate transparency in corporate governance practices.

Adaptation to economic conditions – The analysis of performance changes in relation to Turkey's high inflation period emphasizes the importance of adaptable strategies in corporate governance and financial management. Managers are encouraged to remain agile and responsive to macroeconomic conditions, ensuring that governance and financial strategies are resilient to external pressures.

The findings demonstrate that the SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR method provides managers with a robust tool to comprehensively evaluate corporate performance, as evidenced by AKSA's consistent top performance, highlighting key drivers such as net profit margin and board of directors' score. Its adaptability across different countries and governance systems enables managers to benchmark performance, prioritize strategic initiatives, and enhance both financial outcomes and governance quality.

In summary, this research not only contributes to the academic discourse on corporate governance and FP but also provides actionable insights for managers seeking to enhance organizational performance through a comprehensive, integrated approach. By acknowledging and addressing the interplay between governance and financial outcomes, both researchers and practitioners can foster sustainable corporate success.

8. Conclusions

This study developed DSS by integrating corporate governance performance with the FP indicators. This system addresses the need for comprehensive performance evaluation in corporate settings by synthesizing governance and financial metrics. Traditional performance evaluations have predominantly relied on financial ratios alone, often omitting governance considerations. However, this study emphasizes the value of a dual focus, providing a robust framework for more accurate assessments that recognize both governance structures and financial outcomes in organizational rankings.

The SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method introduced in this research employed the SVTN framework for handling uncertainties and subjective assessments, thereby enhancing the SWARA method's applicability. By integrating linguistic variables into SWARA, the study extends the method's capabilities, enabling more nuanced weight

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assignment for performance indicators. Furthermore, the RBNAR technique was integrated to refine the ranking process. Through reference point-based normalization, RBNAR addressed the limitations of traditional max-min normalization, resulting in more precise rankings.

Application of the proposed method to companies listed on the BIST Corporate Governance Index demonstrated its validity and reliability across multiple years (i.e. 2021, 2022, and 2023). The analysis revealed significant year-over-year differences in governance-FP interactions. The sensitivity analyses confirmed the method's robustness under varying scenarios. Findings showed that "AKSA" consistently achieved the highest governance-based FP, with "net profit margin" and "board of directors score" emerging as the most influential criteria in financial and governance domains, respectively. These results highlighted the efficacy of SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR in identifying high-performing companies based on comprehensive criteria; therefore, it can be effectively applied across different countries and governance systems.

In sum, this research provided a novel methodological contribution by combining corporate governance and the FP metrics into a single framework, thus bridging an important gap in literature. The SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method's ability to yield consistent and reliable results indicates its potential as a valuable tool for decision-makers seeking to evaluate and compare companies holistically. Through its innovative use of MCDM techniques, this research lays the groundwork for further exploration of integrated performance analysis, providing a foundation for future studies to expand on this model and explore its applications in various economic and sectoral contexts.

9. Study Limitations

This study, while pioneering in its approach to integrating corporate governance with the FP evaluation, encounters certain limitations that offer opportunities for future refinement:

Scope limitation of data sources – the study is confined to data from firms listed on the BIST Corporate Governance Index, limiting the generalizability of findings to other markets or regions with distinct governance and regulatory frameworks. Moreover, large datasets require significant time and memory resources.

Temporal limitation in economic context – Given that the study's analysis spans 2021 to 2023, it primarily reflects performance during a period influenced by high inflation in Turkey. Consequently, findings may not fully capture corporate governance dynamics under different economic conditions, such as low-inflation or recessionary environments.

Reliance on selected financial ratios and governance parameters – The model focuses on a specific set of financial ratios (e.g. "net profit margin") and governance criteria (e.g. "board of directors score"). This selection, while impactful, may omit other relevant indicators that could offer further insight into corporate governance-based performance, such as operational efficiency or shareholder relations.

Complexity in implementing the hybrid model – The SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR model's reliance on advanced mathematical and linguistic variables could present challenges

for practitioners unfamiliar with these methods, potentially impacting the practical applicability of the model in industry settings without substantial methodological expertise.

Limited validation across diverse industries – The empirical validation in this study is limited to the industries represented within the BIST Corporate Governance Index. Given that corporate governance frameworks and the FP metrics differ across sectors, the findings may not be directly generalizable without further industry-specific adjustments.

Potential impact of external governance policies – The study does not account for the possible effects of international governance standards or policy changes that could influence corporate governance and performance metrics, particularly in a globalized financial environment.

These limitations highlight areas for future research to refine and extend the model, enabling broader applicability and relevance across varying economic and corporate governance contexts.

10. Future Research Recommendations

This study offers a foundation for integrating corporate governance and FP into a unified DSS, but further exploration is encouraged to expand and deepen the insights into corporate performance. The following recommendations are suggested for future research:

Future studies could apply SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR across different global markets and economies, particularly within emerging or low-inflation environments. Such expansion would allow for a more comprehensive understanding of how economic contexts impact the relationship between corporate governance and FP.

To capture a broader scope of corporate governance impact, future research should explore additional indicators, such as transparency, stakeholder engagement, and sustainability practices, which may offer further insights into companies' governance effectiveness and its influence on financial outcomes.

Considering the impact of economic fluctuations on corporate performance, future research could focus on longitudinal analyses, exploring how external economic factors such as inflation, recession, or currency volatility influence corporate governance and financial outcomes over an extended period.

As industries may have distinct governance structures and performance metrics, conducting industry-specific studies using SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR would allow for tailored insights and enhance the model's relevance and applicability across various sectors.

Future studies could benefit from integrating qualitative assessments, such as management interviews or survey data on governance practices, to provide a more nuanced perspective of the governance-performance relationship, capturing dimensions that may be overlooked by quantitative indicators.

These recommendations aim to broaden the scope and robustness of research on corporate governance-based FP, enhancing the relevance and flexibility of DSSs like the

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SVTN-SWARA-RBNAR hybrid method in both academic and practical applications.

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